

FUNCTION AND STRESS

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Annotation. Stress is the emphasis of any language unit in a speech stream. In English, stress can be used to highlight a syllable, a word, or even an entire phrase. Accordingly, stress can be verbal, syntagmatic and phrasal. Word stress emphasizes a particular syllable in a word. In English transcription, such stress is indicated by a special symbol ['] placed before the stressed syllable. Syntagmatic or tact stress highlights the most important word in one speech tact (syntagma) during the pronunciation of the text. Phrase stress allows you to distinguish several words (syntagma) in a sentence at the same time. Misplaced stress changes the sound of a word, making it difficult to understand. In fluent speech, stress helps distinguish similar words.

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Introduction. Stress is primarily a phonetic concept, since its repetition is possible only with the help of acoustic means - such as intensity, pitch, duration of an accented vowel. Thus, Russian and English are distinguished by a strong accent on the syllable, in Swedish and Japanese, the so-called musical stress, which varies in pitch, is generally accepted.

Phrase stress is one of the most important intonation means of living speech, having not only syntactic, but also logical-semantic and emotional-volitional meaning. Acoustically, phrasal stress is the selection by vocal means of some words or one word in a sentence among others. The functions of phrasal stress are varied. Phrasal stress can be called the intonation center of a sentence. The correct placement of phrasal stress is one of the basic skills without which it is impossible to get rid of the well-known Russian accent. In Russian, unlike English, words in sentences are not so marked by phraseological stress; Therefore, speech in Russian looks more measured. However, there are words that are not stressed in Russian. As a rule, the emphasis does not fall on particles, prepositions, conjunctions "and", "but", as well as personal and possessive pronouns. Due to the large number of words with four or more syllables, the rhythm of speech in Russian is almost imperceptible, and if you pronounce English phrases according to the intonation patterns of the Russian language, then such English speech reading is difficult. it looks like gins.

Phrasal stress in English can include nouns, adjectives, numerals, adverbs, semantic verbs, interrogative and demonstrative pronouns. Auxiliary and modal verbs, verb to be, particle and predicate, conjunction and article, personal and possessive pronouns are pronounced without stress.

In English, one should distinguish three main types of phrasal stress:

1) syntactic, or proper phrasal, 2) logical, 3) emphatic. The need to divide the stress in a sentence into three main types is caused by the following reasons. The division of phrasal stress is dictated, first of all, by the actually existing functional polysemy of stress, that is, it follows from the very essence of phrasal stress. In addition, the purpose of each type is different, and because of this, the forms of their implementation in the language are different.

1. Syntactic stress (or phrasal stress itself) helps convey the general semantic content of a sentence, expressed in syntactically organized lexical units. Syntactic stress is directly related to the syntactic structure of the sentence and word order and, as a rule, highlights significant words in the sentence. The correct distribution of syntactic stress facilitates the perception of the listener's speech, organizes the sentence, and in reading, determines the degree of understanding of the text; in pedagogical terms, it is one of the main conditions for developing meaningful reading skills. The main function of syntactic stress is to convey the general meaning of a sentence together with the grammatical and lexical means of the language.

2. Logical stress aims to particularly highlight the semantic center in a sentence, i.e. serves the purpose of emphasis. With the help of logical stress, the speaker draws the listener's attention to the most important element in the sentence, clarifies the expressed thought, and highlights the logical center of the statement.

3. Phonetics also differentiates emphatic stress, which serves to highlight the emotional center of the statement, the expression of feelings and moods. If there is an emphatic stress in a sentence, additional emotional shades of meaning can be created in it, which are added to the main meaning of the statement and modify it. Emphatic stress can add an emotional component to the logical meaning, which prevails over the logical content. This is the main functional difference between emphatic stress and logical stress. In addition, with emphatic stress the subjective human factor comes to the fore.

Conclusion. Thus, the types of phrasal stress described above do not always appear in their pure form in live oral speech. There are cases of a combination of two types of phrasal stress. Judging by which of the accents is more clearly expressed, we attribute this combination to one type or another. It follows that the divisions of phrasal stress cannot be

placed in the "Procrustean bed" of a frozen scheme. Nevertheless, the presence of transitional cases of stress does not at all refute, but, on the contrary, confirms the need to identify the main types of phrasal stress, characterized by a certain communicative function in order to systematize the study of phrasal stress and facilitate the teaching process.

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